

Milestone 1.2: Analysis of Access policies and legal framework regulating the Access provision

Work package n°	1
Milestone n°	MS 1 / 1.2
Lead beneficiary	F. CEAM
Author(s)	M. Ródenas, A. Muñoz
Deliverable Type	Document
Dissemination Level	PU
Estimated delivery date	M24
Actual delivery date	M24
Version	V1
Reviewed by	
Accepted by	
Comments	

Milestone 1.1: Analysis of Access policies and legal framework regulating the Access provision.

Table of Content

1	Introduction	3
2	Purpose.....	3
3	Overview of existing legal frameworks and policies	3
3.1	List of RIs	3
3.2	European legal frameworks and policies	6
3.3	Policies in existing RIs.....	7
3.3.1	Requisites for Users and eligibility aspects	7
3.3.2	Policy on data storage	8
3.3.3	Data access	8
3.3.4	User’s personal data	9
3.3.5	Reporting and Publications Policy	10
3.3.6	Intellectual Property.....	11
4	Conclusions	12
5	Annex.....	13
5.1	Requisites for Users and eligibility aspects	13
5.2	Policy on data storage	15
5.3	Data access	16
5.4	User’s personal data.....	19
5.5	Reporting and Publications Policy	20
5.6	Intellectual Property Rights	21

1 Introduction

This document has been prepared within the ATMO-ACCESS project and, in particular, it is a milestone of the Work package 1 (WP1): “Developing the concept and guidelines for access to distributed atmospheric Research Infrastructures”. The main objective of WP1 is to define a synergistic framework with guidelines and cost scheme for access to atmospheric Research Infrastructures (RI) to enhance user-friendly and easy access to services provided by atmospheric research facilities in ATMO-ACCESS.

This milestone compiles information for Task 1.2, “Consolidation of access policies and legal framework for atmospheric research infrastructures” reviewing existing access and data policies in RIs. This information will serve as basis to recommend and define a common legal framework for access provision and use of services.

2 Purpose

This milestone analyses and integrates the legal framework regulating the access, data access and use of services in other RIs. It also considers the requirements for common user policy and/or user service agreements to address the scope of rights and responsibilities between facility operators and users for synergistic use of atmospheric facilities, including terms and conditions, access data management, publications, ethical and liability issues, intellectual property rights for different kinds of users.

The document covers:

- Existing European legal frameworks and policies
- Access and data access policies from existing RIs.

3 Overview of existing legal frameworks and policies

3.1 List of RIs

The RIs considered in this document are listed in the Table 1. The list has been obtained by using those RIs in the ESFRI Roadmap related to Environment. It has been completed using as source CORDIS and the official website of the European Commission (<https://ec.europa.eu>), utilizing the words TNA (transnational access) and RI as keywords in the search, along with others which have well developed comprehensive access policies.

Table 1: Research Infrastructures considered for this study

#	RI	Acronym	Scientific area	Life-cycle phase	Website
1	JERICO	Joint European research infrastructure network for coastal observatories	Environment	Operational (non-ESFRI)	https://www.jerico-ri.eu/previous-project/jerico-next/
2	PITHIA-NRF (EISCAT, LOFAR)	Plasmasphere Ionosphere Thermosphere Integrated Research Environment and Access services: a Network of Research Facilities	Environment	Operational (non-ESFRI)	https://pithia-nrf.eu/
3	ECCSEL ERIC	European Carbon Dioxide Capture and Storage Laboratory Infrastructure	Environment	Operational (ESFRI, Landmark)	https://www.eccsel.org/
4	ACTRIS	Aerosols, Clouds and Trace gases Preparatory Phase Project	Environment	Implementation (ESFRI, Landmark)	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/739530
5	eLTER RI	European long-term ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems research infrastructure PLUS	Environment	Implementation (ESFRI, Project)	https://elter-ri.eu/elter-plus
6	INTERACT	International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic	Environment	Operational (non-ESFRI, Project)	www.eu-interact.org
7	ENVRI PLUS	Environmental Research Infrastructures Providing Shared Solutions for Science and Society	Environment	Operational (ESFRI and non-ESFRIs network)	https://www.envriplus.eu/
8	AIDA-2000 (CERN, KIT, JSI, UoB, etc)	Advanced European Infrastructures for Detectors	Environment, energy, technology	Operational (non-ESFRI, Project)	https://aida2020.web.cern.ch/aida2020/

9	NFFA-Europe	Free transnational access to boost nanoscience	Physical Sciences	Closure (non-ESFRI, H2020 project)	https://www.nffa.eu/news/project-updates/pilot-nep/
10	BBMRI-ERIC	European Research Infrastructure for Biobanking and Biomolecular Resources	Health and Food	Operational (ESFRI, Landmark)	https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/
11	EUROVOLC	European Network of Observatories and Research Infrastructures for Volcanology	Environment	Closure (non-ESFRI, H2020 project)	https://eurovolc.eu/
12	ERIGrid	Smart Grid Systems Technology Development	Physical Sciences	Operational (non-ESFRI, H2020 project)	https://erigrd2.eu/
13	EU_FT-CR_MS	Fourier-Transform Ion-Cyclotron-Resonance Mass Spectrometry Centers	Environment, Technology	Operational (non-ESFRI, H2020 project)	https://www.eu-fticr-ms.eu/
14	AQUACOSM-EU	EU network of mesocosms facilities for research on marine and freshwater ecosystems	Environment	Operational (non-ESFRI, H2020 INFRAIA)	https://www.aquacosm.eu/
15	ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observation System	Environment	Operational (ESFRI, Landmark)	www.icos-ri.eu
16	Euro-ARGO	European contribution to the international Argo Programme	Environment	Operational (ESFRI, Landmark)	http://www.euro-argo.eu/
17	IAGOS	In-service Aircraft for a Global Observing System	Environment	Operational (ESFRI, Landmark)	http://www.iagos.org/
18	EMSO ERIC	European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water-column Observatory	Environment	Operational (ESFRI, Landmark)	http://www.emso.eu/
19	EPOS ERIC	European Plate Observing System	Environment	Implementation (ESFRI, Landmark)	http://www.epos-eu.org/

3.2 European legal frameworks and policies

This access policy takes into account the overall European legal framework related to environmental data, information and databases, health and safety at work. Related normative can be found in the following directives and guidelines:

- Aarhus Convention (access to environmental data),
- The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), 2016/679, is a Regulation in EU law on data protection and privacy in the EU and the European Economic Area (EEA). for the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data,
- Council Directive 89/391/EEC of 12 June 1989 on the introduction of measures to encourage improvements in the safety and health of workers at work,
- Directive 2007/2/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 March 2007 on establishing an Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community (INSPIRE) (sharing of the spatial information among public sector organisations and access to the spatial data),
- Directive 96/9/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 March 1996 on the legal protection of databases,
- Directive 2009/24/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the legal protection of computer programs,
- Directive 2003/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 November 2003 on the re-use of public sector information and amendments to it,
- European Charter for Access to Research Infrastructures (principles and guidelines for access policies),
- OECD Principles and Guidelines for Access to Research Data from Public Funding.

3.3 Policies in existing RIs

Different access and data access regulations addressed in the RIs and projects on networks of RIs considered in the preparation of this document are shown. Aspects covered are summarized in this document and have been organized into different topics. Specific details directly extracted from the RI's legislation is collected in the annex, given an overview of specific regulations.

In general, the policies reviewed are structured around the principles of **Open Science**, aiming to democratize access to research data and promote transparency, collaboration, and innovation and **FAIR** (findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable). Many of those RIs are part of the ESFRI Roadmap of RIs, which includes a data policy that aims to promote open access to data and managed according to the FAIR principles, while ensuring appropriate protection of personal data and commercial interests. It also promotes the development of data management plans. The ESFRI Data Policy also requires that personal data are handled in compliance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and that commercial interests are protected by ensuring that intellectual property rights are respected. Overall, the ESFRI Data Policy aims to ensure that research infrastructures promote the use and reuse of data, while respecting ethical, legal, and commercial considerations.

3.3.1 Requisites for Users and eligibility aspects

The requisites for users of RIs are designed to ensure that the infrastructure is used safely, efficiently and effectively, and that the research conducted using the infrastructure meets high scientific and ethical standards. Principles covered typically related to the fulfillment of certain qualifications or specific expertise by the users in order to use the infrastructure; certain safety requirements; to demonstrate that the research project is of high quality and has the potential to make a significant contribution to the scientific community and/or to comply with ethical and legal requirements. Aspects addressed in the reviewed policies and how these are treated are shown below:

- Principal investigator affiliated to an organization in a different country, except in EMSO ERIC, where there is no restriction regarding the country of origin of the user.
- Access modes and selection criteria: e.g. scientific, technical and market-driven
- Agreement on dissemination of research outcomes and open data

- Applicable laboratory, national and international laws and regulations and compliance
- Eligibility for funding
- Travel and health insurance

3.3.2 Policy on data storage

The Data Policy aims at setting the principles to govern the collection, storage and management of research data. It aims at ensuring the FAIR principles for data: findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, and that data are collected and managed ethically, and in compliance with relevant laws, regulations, and ethical guidelines.

The policies consulted relate to data storage. For instance, NFFA-Europe has developed a detailed policy, stating that the project is responsible for managing public data and providing access to the project's database through a frontend website and applications. Also, Data Repository will contain metadata and rules for data access, and may be associated with institutions or instruments. The actual retention period for data will depend on the type and volume of data, and NFFA-Europe reserves the right to reduce the retention period, while Data and metadata are kept confidential for eighteen months before being made open access, with some exceptions. The research infrastructure is responsible for maintaining research data and metadata for a period of ten years, and the Data Repository is an operational system for managing digital resources. Policies relate to the following topics:

- Public Data Management.
- Data Repository.
- Retention Period.
- Research Data and Metadata Maintenance.
- Data Repository Management.
- Metadata Definition.
- Confidentiality and Access.

3.3.3 Data access

The policy on management of research data refers to guidelines and regulations covering ownership, curation and access to research data and metadata collected in the access. The goal of such policies is to ensure the integrity, accuracy, and reliability of research data and to facilitate

their long-term preservation and accessibility for future use. Its implementation ensure that research data are managed effectively, shared appropriately, and preserved for future use, promoting the responsible use of data. To ensure that research data are managed and made accessible for use and reuse, the policy also includes a metadata schema and policy in case of deliberate infringements of the policy.

In general, documentation reviewed promotes the principles FAIR and Open science to govern the data access to make research data accessible while also ensuring compliance with national and European legislation. Users are required to comply with national and European legislation, as well as the RI's data policy.

The policies outline the ownership, curation, and access of research data and metadata collected during the access. Nevertheless, access to data may be limited in certain circumstances, such as when it could compromise personal data protection or confidentiality rules, affect the human subject or the protection of endangered species, or infringe on intellectual property rights or commercial sensitivity.

Questions regulated in the documentation reviewed are:

- Compliance with national and European legislation
- Users are classified into different levels in respect of access rights and restrictions
- Ownership, curation, and access to research data and metadata
- Rights to use data
- Reasonable limitations and restrictions
- Metadata standard definition
- Infringements

3.3.4 User's personal data

The policy on retention of user's information sets guidelines and regulations on individuals' right to access and correct their personal information that has been collected and used as part of the access to the RI, i.e. before or during the access. It is designed to protect the privacy and confidentiality of research participants and helps to guarantee privacy and confidentiality informing the individuals about their right to access and correct their personal information.

The EU implemented the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in 2018, which is a comprehensive data protection regulation setting out the rules for the collection, use, handling, storage, deletion and processing of personal data of individuals within the EU. It applies to any organization, whether located within or outside the EU, that processes personal data of individuals within the EU and the failure to comply with it can result in significant fines and penalties.

Under the GDPR, organizations that handle personal data must comply with certain principles, including transparency, purpose limitation, data minimization, accuracy, storage limitation, and confidentiality. They must also obtain explicit consent from individuals for collecting and using their personal data, and provide them with the right to access, correct, and delete their data.

The different RI policies reviewed indeed refer to this legislation and, complying with the GDPR legislation, define the level, content and retention period of the data collected. Aspect addressed are:

- Information collected
- Period of personal data retention
- Storage conditions of personal data: where, how
- Pseudonymization of personal data
- User's rights to correct and cancel their data
- Right to request personal data

3.3.5 Reporting and Publications Policy

Reporting and publication refers to the guidelines and rules that researchers and publishers must follow when reporting and disseminating scientific findings to the scientific community and the general public. These policies are designed to ensure that scientific research is conducted and reported in an ethical, transparent, and rigorous manner. Policies reviewed refer to the following aspects:

- Delivery time for reporting actions after the end of the access
- Content of metadata accompanying the data

- Consideration of data and metadata as publication data
- Encouragement to publish results in journals, conferences, etc. and as open as possible
- Open access repositories
- Reporting and acknowledgement
- Offer of co-authorship in publications using the RI's data

3.3.6 Intellectual Property

Intellectual property rights refer to the legal protections afforded to scientific discoveries, inventions, and other forms of intellectual property. It can include patents, trademarks, copyrights, etc.

The RI policies consulted recommend to license publications and data using Creative Commons Attribution International Public License, Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication or equivalent, and they encourage the use of open access licenses. The most recommended license is *CC BY*: This license lets others distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon your work, even commercially, as long as they credit you for the original creation, this is the case for ICOS, IAGOS, ACTRIS, while EPOS proposes two modalities: *CC BY* and also *CC BY NC*, with restrictions on the use for commercial use.

In general, the policies agree on include acknowledgment, authorship and intellectual property for patents, publications data and products resulting from the access, but also for the use of jointly owned research. Some exceptions are addressed (ACTRIS), for example, when use of the results could jeopardize a potential industrial/commercial use, violate the rules on personal data protection or on confidentiality for security reasons, or for any other legitimate reason to be agreed upon in writing case by case basis.

Aspects addressed in the regulations are:

- Usage of jointly owned results
- Ownership and intellectual property rights to any data or data related tools, databases, software, prototypes, new tools or methodologies or any other products that are generated in relation to the access
- Attribution and respect for intellectual property

- Publication data licensing and attribution
- Acknowledgement of support and ownership of data
- Intellectual property rights and commercial use
- Recommended licenses for open data access
- Ownership and warranties of data and products
- Reuse of data
- Respect for third party intellectual property rights
- Exceptions to Expected access rights.

4 Conclusions

A search of policies regulating the access provision to RIs has been done. In general, FAIR and open Access science are promoted with higher or lower detail. Similarities and agreement among the policies have been found, with no relevant discrepancies. Some RIs present an advanced legal maturity and have developed extensive regulation, tackling the aspects addressed in this document in their internal policies (ACTRIS, NFFA-Europe, INTERACT, EPOS-ERIC, etc) while regulation is scarce in others, e.g. the use of user's personal data is not in general treated, not even referred to the GDPR legislation. On the other hand, regulation applied to SMEs not widely addressed and deserves special attention.

Even though the ACTRIS has elaborated a comprehensive legislation, it can be revisited and improved with inputs from other RI legislations. Indeed, the information collected in this document will serve as basis for future recommendations and establishment of common guidelines and policies regulating the access provision.

5 Annex

This annex collects specific policies from the RIs reviewed. Even though not all the policies are included and more details are given in the RI documentation, it gives an overview and examples of existing regulations that apply to RI access provision. RIs and projects from where the policy have been extracted is indicated in parenthesis.

5.1 Requisites for Users and eligibility aspects

- User group leader or the sole user must be affiliated to an organization in a country other than the country where the site they wish to access is located (eLTER PLUS, JERICO, and JERICO-NEXT).
- Applications will be selected according to defined criteria and access modes (Excellence-driven access mode, Technical need-driven access mode, and Market-driven access mode). In case of peer-review, a specific panel will be set up for scientific and technical evaluation. The composition and the functioning of the panel are based on principles of transparency, fairness and impartiality (ACTRIS).
- Prior to receiving access, user groups must confirm that they intend to disseminate the outcomes of their study conducted under the eLTER PLUS TA-RA Scheme (eLTER PLUS).
- RIs should support users to be compliant with any applicable national/regional/local law and regulations, as well as health and safety requirements, facilitating the production of the needed documentation. RIs may also consider setting up a "user code of conduct" which may facilitate users to comply with the requirements (ENVRI PLUS).
- Read Information for Applicants and Research Plan Instructions. They contain the information to fill in the application properly, including the budgeting and cost specifications, and content and structure of required attachments (INTERACT).
- Users working for an organization which is an eLTER PLUS beneficiary, are in principle eligible for receiving TA and/or RA funding, but limitations apply (eLTER PLUS).
- Users not working in a European Union Member State or H2020 Associated Country are eligible, provided they do not form the majority within the respective user group. However, well founded exceptions are possible (eLTER PLUS).

- All user group members must have an appropriate travel and health insurance and be clear about the legal responsibilities of their employers (INERACT).
- If the beneficiary is an ERIC which does not have its own resources, it may exceptionally delegate the following responsibilities to one of its members (AIDA-2020):
 - monitor that the action is implemented properly.
 - inform about events or circumstances likely to affect significantly or delay the action implementation.
 - submit deliverables and reports.
 - submit documents or information required.
- User group leader and the majority of the users must work in a country other than the country(ies) where the installation is located; Transnational access cannot be granted to an infrastructure/installation that is located in the same country where the user works. In other words, applicants are not eligible for TA to their national infrastructures (Interact, ACTRIS).
- Research centres, universities, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and large companies are eligible to benefit from access to EMSO facilities. A single PI, researcher, PhD student or research engineer is also eligible to participate in the programme. There is no restriction regarding the country of origin of the user (EMSO ERIC)
- Contract will be signed: A three party written contract or agreement between the “Access Provider” or host facility, the “End User” or applicant and the “Call Coordinator” or EMSO ERIC will delineate the actions to be undertaken, the resources that will need to be allocated, the length of planned user stays (if any), and the period of use. It will also define the rights and obligations of all the Parties involved, including data sharing and eventual provisions for early termination of the conferred access. It will also clearly define the Intellectual Property Rights policy in case the project yields a patent or a commercial product (EMSO ERIC).

5.2 Policy on data storage

- ECCSEL ERIC OC will be responsible for keeping track of all the Public Data that will be produced and will manage the frontend website and applications that will serve to structure and display the access to ECCSEL ERIC Database (ECCSEL).
- The Data Repository contains Metadata about the Datasets, as well as given rules for data access. A Data Repository may be associated with a certain Institution or a group of them, or a certain Instrument or a group of them, or may be run by a third-party. Data Repositories may or may not be directly used by Research Users (NFFA-EUROPE).
- The actual retention period will depend on the type and volume of data and the economic consequences associated with long-term data storage. Thus, NFFA-Europe reserves the right to reduce the retention period in consultation with the respective Beneficiaries in charge of it (NFFA-EUROPE).
- NFFA-Europe research infrastructure is responsible for a long-term period of ten years to maintain Research Data and Metadata within the platforms and tools made available by the project. The actual retention period will depend on the type and volume of data and the economic consequences associated with long-term data storage (NFFA-EUROPE).
- Operational information system for managing and organizing digital resources, particularly suitable for Datasets or Publication Data which are not likely to be altered again. The Data Repository contains Metadata about the Datasets, as well as given rules for data access (NFFA-EUROPE).
- NFFA-EUROPE Definition of Metadata: set of descriptive, structural and contextual information describing the context, content and structure of Research Data and/or Datasets and their management through time. It describes information pertaining to research projects, including (but not limited to) the context of the Experiment, the Research Users, the Data Analysis methods, and other logistical information (NFFA-EUROPE). NFFA-Europe research infrastructure is the custodian of all the Research Data and Metadata stored in the platforms and tools made available by the project and used in the services offered as Virtual Access. It is responsible for a long-term period of ten

years to maintain Research Data and Metadata within the platforms and tools made available by the project (NFFA-EUROPE).

- The data and metadata will be kept confidential for eighteen months after their sending to the User's Group Leader. After this period the data and metadata will be put in open access. This period may be extended for another period of twelve months by sending a justified request to the PI of the EU_FT-ICR_MS installation with copy to the PI of the EU_FT-ICR_MS Research Infrastructure (EU_FT-ICR_MS and AIDA-2020).

The confidentiality obligations no longer apply if:

- the disclosing party agrees to release the other party
 - the information was already known by the recipient or is given to him without obligation of confidentiality by a third party that was not bound by any obligation of confidentiality
 - the recipient proves that the information was developed without the use of confidential information
 - the information becomes generally and publicly available, without breaching any confidentiality obligation, or
 - the disclosure of the information is required by EU or national law (AIDA)
- The Persistent Digital Identifiers (PID) or Digital Object Identifier (DOI) of the data object will be provided and will always resolve to its landing page when submitting data to the handle system (ICOS, IAGOS).

5.3 Data access

- All proceedings related to access and sharing must be compliant with national and European legislation such as the Directive 95/46/EC and, as of 28 May 2018, the EU General Data Protection Regulation and a Code of Conduct (GDPR Article 40). If none of the above is applicable, it must be compliant with national legislation. (BBMRI-ERIC).
- NFFA-Europe Research Data Policy covers ownership, curation and access to Research Data and Metadata collected during Transnational Access activities, in-house research and Joint Activities within the NFFA-Europe PILOT project (NFFA-EUROPE).

- Users shall give to the ACTRIS ERIC a worldwide, free of charge, perpetual, transferable, non-exclusive right to use for any purpose the data and related documents generated by them within the Physical, Remote or Virtual access. This right includes, but is not restricted to, the right to modify, reproduce, sublicense, incorporate to other data, other databases or other tools as well as produce new developments (ACTRIS-ERIC).
- Reasonable limitations and restrictions, still in line with the principle of open access, may be applied when, especially for data, the access could compromise a potential industrial or commercial use of the data, or when the access could lead to a breach in personal data protection or confidentiality rules, or when the access could affect the human subject or the protection of endangered species (ENVRI PLUS).
- Access limitations may also occur in order to respect potential Intellectual Property Rights, trade secrets, commercial sensitivity or to protect the confidentiality of certain information which may not be accessible for research (ENVRI PLUS).
- Regarding Data produced outside Access, ECCSEL will be considered as the sole Data Owner (ECCSEL).
- Goal of the project is to have all data produced during the lifetime of the project to be findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR) (AQUACOSM-EU).
- Present Research Data Policy covers ownership, curation and access to Research Data and Metadata collected during Transnational Access activities, in-house research and Joint Activities within the NFFA-Europe PILOT project (NFFA-EUROPE).
- Policy aims to ensure that Research Data generated in the NFFA-Europe PILOT project are managed and made accessible for use and reuse (NFFA-EUROPE).
- Metadata Schema that fulfills the needs of a scientific community, has obtained consensus, and has been ratified as a standard by some official bodies, such as the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative or the NeXus Data Format (NFFA-EUROPE).
- Overview of existing Metadata Standards organized by discipline can be found on the Research Data Alliance's Metadata Standards Directory (NFFA-EUROPE).

- Deliberate infringements of this policy may lead to denial of access to Research Data and Metadata, and/or denial of future access to the NFFA-Europe research infrastructure (NFFA-EUROPE).
- Within EPOS Data Policy, “Users” in respect of access rights and restrictions, are classified as follows (EPOS ERIC):
 - Anonymous: Access without any identification or accreditation is not permitted at the ICS level. However, if a TCS decide to grant anonymous access, the TCS should provide alternative mechanisms to monitor use and purposes to which DDSS use is being applied.
 - Registered: Identified access requiring prior registration, which may differ from specific EPOS services.
 - Authorised: Identified and authenticated access requiring specific permissions for particular DDSS or EPOS services to identified user group(s). Only a Registered user can become an Authorised user.
- Within EPOS Data Policy, “Access to DDSS (data)”, with regard to access rights and restrictions, may be classified as follows (EPOS ERIC):
 - Open: DDSS freely available/accessible to User(s) either for download or for direct use within an EPOS Service.
 - Restricted: DDSS that are available under the conditions set out by the SP. Restrictions to specific type of user categories, if any, should be limited to specific datasets. Restrictions may also mean that fees could be charged. While metadata shall always be available at no charge, fees, if any, should no higher than the actual cost of making the DDSS available.
 - Embargoed: DDSS that are available only after a predefined limited time (embargo period - that cannot exceed 3 years) has passed since collection/generation. Once the embargo period has passed, DDSS may become either Open or Restricted.
- Metadata (and DDSS descriptions) are always free and available at any time, even for restricted and embargoed data.

5.4 User's personal data

- Personal data are retained for the duration of the EUROVOLC project. However, the User can ask at any time to interrupt the processing of the data or have data canceled (EUROVOLC and EurofleetsPlus).
- We collect your personal information using online forms, the data of which is stored on EUROVOLC's account on Jotform.com; accessible only to the EUROVOLC TA and dissemination coordinators); in this framework the Jotform standalone form links and embed codes are secure (SSL) by default, and the data is secure as Jotform adheres to strict General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in Europe, and the data is stored on secure German servers (EUROVOLC).
- 'Pseudonymisation' means the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person (BBMRI-ERIC).
- Users have the right to have access to their personal information, and to have this information corrected and amended (EUROVOLC).
- At the end of their occupancy of the Infrastructure, all Users shall sign a record of presence at the Infrastructure, giving their nationality, their place of work, date of birth, contact details, and the duration of access to the Infrastructure (Project HYDRALAB+).
- The EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) applies to 'personal data' meaning any information relating to an identifiable person who can be directly or indirectly identified in particular by reference to an identifier. The GDPR applies to all handling of personal data such as how to collect, handle, store and delete the data (INTERACT).
- Under GDPR you have a right to request a copy of your personal data held by EMSO. EMSO is required to fulfill this request within 20 working days (EMSO-LINK). Reporting and Publications Policy

5.5 Reporting and Publications Policy

- UG must fulfill the reporting and dissemination commitments, specified in the access contract. Two mandatory reporting actions must be accomplished by the UG within two months after the end of the access (ERIGrid).
- Recipients must consider “Publication Data” any Research Data generated in the project (Raw Data and/or Analyzed Data), including associated Metadata, needed to validate the results presented in a Scientific Publication or appearing in it; Metadata has to include information about any other tools and instruments needed to re-use or validate the data (e.g. specialized software or software code, algorithms and analysis protocols) (NFFA-EUROPE).
- UG is encouraged to publish the results in journals, conferences, etc. As soon as they are accepted for publication or published, the UG will provide detailed information to the ERIGrid 2.0 Lab Access Manager and the ERIGrid 2.0 Project Coordinator on the corresponding abstracts, papers, reports, conference presentations, etc. related to the access activity. Preferably, open access publications should be chosen (ERIGrid, NFFA-EUROPE, and ECCSEL).
- Users are normally expected to make their publications available through open access repositories (ACTRIS).
- Any publications or patents resulting from the JERICO-S3 TA project must be reported to the host institute and the JERICO-S3 TA office. Furthermore, all such publications or patents shall acknowledge the support of the European Commission’s H2020 Framework Programme under grant agreement No. 871153, JERICO-S3 Transnational Access program, and the host institute (JERICO).
- Any publications or patents resulting from the JERICO-NEXT TNA project must be reported to the host institute and the JERICO-NEXT TNA office. Furthermore, all such publications or patents shall acknowledge the support of the European Commission’s H2020 Framework Programme under grant agreement No. 654410, JERICO-NEXT Trans National Access program, and the host institute (JERICO-NEXT).

- Users of IAGOS data products are required to offer co-authorship to the IAGOS Principal Investigators if the IAGOS data play a significant role in the publication (IAGOS).

5.6 Intellectual Property Rights

- Each of the Joint Owners shall be entitled to use the Jointly Owned RESULTS solely for non-commercial research and development purposes on a royalty-free, non-exclusive, non-transferable basis as long as the protection of such Jointly Owned RESULTS is not adversely affected (ERIGrid).
- Data are licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International licence (CC BY 4.0) (ICOS, IAGOS), stating that:

You are free to:

- Share, copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format
- Adapt, remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially

Under the following terms:

- Attribution You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the licence, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.
 - No additional restrictions — You may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the licence permits.
- Attribution: The intellectual investment of investigators involved in the creation of data registries and bio-repositories is often substantial, and should be acknowledged. This should be specified in Material and Data Transfer Agreements (MTA/DTA) signed by both parties (BBMRI-ERIC).
 - Respect for intellectual property: Sharing of data and biological samples needs to be performed in a way that protects intellectual property rights of the parties involved. It also needs to address the requirements of institutions and third-party funders (BBMRI-ERIC).

- Publication Data must be published using the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or a license with equivalent rights (NFFA-EUROPE).
- Anybody reusing Publication Data must comply with the indicated licensing terms and are invited to cite the unique identifier as well as any Scientific Publications linked to the same Publication Data, if available and appropriate (NFFA-EUROPE).
- Publications or patents shall acknowledge the support of the European Commission's H2020 Framework Programme under grant agreement No.871153, JERICO-S3 Transnational Access program, and the host institute (JERICO).
- Data collected or generated during a EUROVOLC TA activity, will be owned by the user (i.e. the team that generated it). However, if a TA proposal requests scientific collaboration with the TA provider during the access activity, then the data ownership should be shared by the user and the provider. In such cases a joint ownership agreement should be signed before the access starts (EUROVOLC).
- If a patent or commercial product is to be obtained, the intellectual property rights (IPR) will be negotiated at the time of signing the access contract (EMOS-Link).
- RIs are expected to use licenses that provide legal clarity about open data access, use, sharing, and exploitation of RI data, and give explicit permission to use work created by the owner (ENVRI PLUS).
- It is recommended to use licenses that (ENVRI PLUS):
 - include the attribution condition to ensure that credits are given to the author,
 - are applicable to most jurisdictions,
 - allow copying and redistribution of the material in any medium or format, and to remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially
- Anybody reusing Publication Data must comply with the indicated licensing terms and are invited to cite the unique identifier as well as any Scientific Publications linked to the same Publication Data, if available and appropriate (NFFA-EUROPE).

- Ownership and intellectual property rights to any data or data related tools, databases, software, prototypes, new tools or methodologies or any other products that are generated in relation to the access shall belong to those who have generated them in accordance with the applicable legislation (ACTRIS-ERIC).
- No warranties are given by the ACTRIS ERIC, the National Facilities, the Data Centre or the Topical Centres and they disclaim any express and implied warranties of non-infringement of third party intellectual property rights, patentability, safety, industrial or commercial suitability or fitness for a particular purpose of the data, tools, products or services provided in accordance with this policy (ACTRIS-ERIC).
- Third party rights are intellectual property rights that the ACTRIS ERIC, the National Facilities and/or the Central Facilities have not generated themselves and do not own. If ACTRIS ERIC, the National Facilities, or the Central Facilities use such third-party rights as part of their own intellectual property, they have to ensure that the intellectual property rights of the third parties are respected and that they have the authorisation of the right holders to grant access rights in accordance with this policy (ACTRIS-ERIC).
- For justified and legitimate reasons ACTRIS ERIC may allow exceptions to the expected access rights, for example, when use of the results by ACTRIS could jeopardize a potential industrial/commercial use, violate the rules on personal data protection or on confidentiality for security reasons, or for any other legitimate reason to be agreed upon in writing case by case basis. Such exceptions are agreed upon with the ACTRIS ERIC (ACTRIS-ERIC, EPOS ERIC).
- If a patent or commercial product is to be obtained, the intellectual property rights (IPR) will be negotiated at the time of signing the access contract. If the project is entirely funded by the user, the user will keep the IPR and all knowledge derived from the project (EMSO ERIC).
- EPOS aims to grant one default licence set for EPOSmanaged DDSS, Creative Commons 4.0. Within the Creative Commons permitted licence scheme, two licences will be adopted, CC:BY and CC:BY:NC. SP(s) have the possibility, provided it is agreed with Suppliers, where no licence type is identified to apply/affix a licence on unlicensed data on the Supplier's

behalf. Nevertheless, Suppliers will be encouraged to affix open licenses, preferably Creative Commons 4.0 CC:BY, to their metadata (EPOS ERIC).